

Meet PEPPER

PEPPER is a research and innovation project accelerating the transition to sustainable green hydrogen production, funded by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership under the Horizon Europe Programme.

Grant Agreement ID:
101192341
Duration:
1st January 2025 – 31st December 2027

PEPPER Consortium

8 partners | 6 countries

Coordinator

DLR (Germany)

Partners

AVL (Austria)

CEA (France)

CNRS (France)

DTU (Denmark)

EIFER (Germany)

ELCOGEN (Estonia)

GRANT GARANT (Czechia)

CNRS Affiliated Entities

Institut des matériaux
de Nantes Jean Rouxel (France)

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Université de Technologie
Belfort-Montbéliard (France)

Find Out More About PEPPER

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The project is supported by the
Clean Hydrogen Partnership
and its members.

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Performant and Efficient Planar Proton-conducting Electrolysis Reactor

Spicing Up Hydrogen Innovation

The Hydrogen Challenge

Green hydrogen is essential for a climate-neutral future. It powers heavy industries like steel, chemicals, and transport without releasing emissions – a powerful tool in the fight against climate change. Yet current technologies can't keep up with the growing demand. They struggle with high energy use, dependence on critical raw materials, and are difficult to scale up, leaving a gap in the path to sustainable hydrogen production.

Our Mission

PEPPER aims to develop the next generation of high efficiency hydrogen electrolyzers based on planar proton conducting ceramic electrolysis cells (PCCELS).

Advance PCCEL technology operating at 400–600 °C, improving efficiency and sustainability by using industrial waste heat in the form of steam.

Develop two scalable cell designs – cermet-supported and metal-supported.

Integrate cells into compact short stacks for validation and testing.

Set PCCEL technology on the path to real world industrial deployment.

PEPPER Technology

PCCEL is an innovative hydrogen technology operating at ~600 °C, turning steam into green hydrogen. How it works:

- 1 H_2O in the form of steam enters the oxygen electrode (positrode).
- 2 Electrolysis splits H_2O into oxygen gas and protons, with protons (H^+) moving through the ceramic electrolyte.
- 3 At the negatrode, protons combine with electrons to form pure hydrogen, which can be electrochemically compressed, reducing energy use for storage and transport.

PCCEL at work

PEPPER's planar cell design allows compact and easily scalable stacks. Combined with metal-supported cells, it cuts the use of critical raw materials by up to 90% and enables cost-effective manufacturing.

PEPPER Stack

PEPPER Performance Goals

At least 20 %

less electricity consumption compared to low temperature electrolysis

Up to 90 %

reduction in critical raw materials through metal supported design

At least 90 %

Faraday efficiency

Enhanced Tolerance

to acidic contaminants like Si and Cr species

Scalable

~ 100 cm² cell size suitable for industrial application

Shaping the Future

PEPPER's long-term impact on industry, energy, and the environment:

Helps industrial decarbonization

Contributes to EU hydrogen production sovereignty

Increases efficiency and sustainability by recycling industrial waste heat

Supports EU Green Deal goals